

THE SOUNDS OF ENGLISH

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This is a **practical guide** on English pronunciation, covering vowel and consonant sounds, intonation, and connected speech.

Key Points:

1. Objectives:

- Understand different sounds in English.
- Improve pronunciation.

2. Content:

- Detailed instruction on vowel and consonant sounds, including short, long, and diphthong vowels.
- Comprehensive coverage of intonation patterns, such as falling, rising, and mixed intonation, with practical examples.
- Activities and quizzes designed to reinforce learning and test understanding.
- Video links to supplementary resources that provide auditory examples and additional practice opportunities.

The sounds of English

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- **Objectives:**

- **English:**

- Understand the sounds in English
- Pronounce the sounds in English
- Get familiar with linking words and connected speech
- Learn some differences between British English and American English

- **Social and technological:**

- learn how to use digital tools to **learn English online**
- promote **student online interaction** and active **participation**
- Learn different tools to **learn English off-line** (Moodle, websites, etc)

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

PROBLEM

English: A Non-Phonetic Language

THE WAY YOU **PRONOUNCE** AND YOU **SPELL** A WORD IS DIFFERENT

-ee	-ea	-e_e
feet	eagle	these
sheep	pea	theme

/i:/

HOMOPHONES

 flew	
 sea	
 right	

/u:/

/i:/

/ai/

• IMPORTANT FACTORS TO CONSIDER FOR VOWEL SOUNDS

- **LENGHT**

- **CONTEXT** (next sounds)

- VOWEL LENGTH**

Long		Short	
/i:/	Heat	/ɪ/	Hit
	Feet		Fit
/u:/	Hoot	/ʊ/	Hood
	Fool		Full
/ɔ/	Short	/ɒ/	Shot
	Caught		Cot

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **PRONOUNCE THEM -**
- HARD / HAD
- SEAT / SIT
- Port / pot
- Look / luke

• Context: vowels followed by

R

for**k** /fɔ:k/
bir**d** /bɜ:d/
car**t** /kɑ:t/

L

hal**f** UK:*/'hɑ:f/
Pal**m** UK:*/'pɑ:m/
tal**k** UK:*/'tɔ:k/
Wal**k** UK:*/'wɔ:k/

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- PRONOUNCE THEM
- park / car / far
- Half / Palm / calm

QUIZ

- Are these vowel sounds long or short?
- Walk
- Hard
- Had
- Bad
- Lord
- Horse
- put

MIDDLE A/E ex. had

SHORT ex. hut

LONG ex. heart

•LONG A

a	BATH
ar	FAR
al	HALF
au	LAUGH
ear	HEART

- LONG A
- Watch the following video (BBC)
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uDHMuMQdBNw>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

• SHORT A

/ʌ/

- BUN
- SHUT
- NOTHING
- LOVE
- ENOUGH
- FLOOD
- DOES

- SHORT A
- Watch the following video
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TNFKG0yvDx4>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Youtube)

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **MIDDLE A/E**

/ a /

BACK
MAD
STAND
HATCH
FANTASTIC

- Middle A
- Watch this video
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qVhaIHk88a8>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

MINIMAL PAIRS: LONG AND SHORT A

[hæt]

[hɑːt]

[hʌt]

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **Quiz** – Are they long / short / middle?

- HARD
- RAT
- BARD
- BUT
- BAD
- MUST
- PARK
- LAUGH

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

NOW **PRONOUNCE** THEM

- RAT
- BAD

- BUT
- MUST

- PARK
- start

LONG E
ex. bird

SHORT E
ex. ten

• LONG E

er

PERCH

ear

LEARN

ir

BIRD

or

WORD

ur

TURN

- **LONG E**

- Watch this video

-

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zSJJWHymEPw>

- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

•SHORT E

e

T**E**N

M**E**N

ea

H**E**AD

B**R**EAD

ai

S**A**ID

- SHORT E
- Watch this video
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hLN1cdSTDo8>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **Quiz** – Are they long or short vowel sounds?
- Girl
- Pen
- Bird
- Red
- Turn
- Bed
- Learn
- pet

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **PRONOUNCE** THEM

- Girl
- Bird
- Turn
- learn

- Ten
- bed
- Pen
- red

LONG I

ex. SEAT

SHORT I

ex. SIT

• LONG I

ee

PEE

ea

READ

SEAT

•SHORT I

i

SiT

LIP

Y

MITH

- Long and Short I
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TNFKG0yvDx4>
- Source: BBC Learning English

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **Quiz** – Are they long or short vowel sounds?
- READ
- BIT
- SEA
- BEE
- BEACH
- SIT
- PEE

- **PRONOUNCE** the following words:

- READ

- SEA

- BEE

- BEACH

- TEACH

- BIT

- BITCH

- SHIP

- LIP

• Activity

- Match words with the **SAME** vowel sound

READ

BATH

LEARN

MUST

PIN

SIT

PEN

CAT

BEACH

BREAD

BUT

SAD

WORD

HARD

LONG O
Ex. door

SHORT O
Ex. dog

•LONG O

or	FOR
oor	DOOR
o(c)e	MORE
al	TALK
ar	WARM
au	CAUGHT
aw	SAW

- Long O
- Watch the following video:
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KHlIC40_u1Q
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **PRONOUNCE** THESE WORDS:

- DOOR

- WALK

- CORN

- FORK

• **SHORT O**

o

DOG

a

WATCH

au

AUSTRIA

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- Short O
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MAk-XtHsyzM>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **PRONOUNCE** THESE WORDS:
- HOT
- TOP
- JOB
- GOD
- LOT
- SOCK

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **QUIZ** Are these sound vowels LONG or SHORT?

WALK

SOCK

MORE

WARM

NOT

SAW

GOT

SON

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

LONG U
Ex. food

LONG U
Ex. put

• LONG U

oo

FOOD

ou

YOU

wo

TWO

o

WHO

u + e

LUKE

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- Long U
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mnKEGLuEzV4>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **PRONOUNCE** THESE WORDS:

- YOU

- FOOD

- TWO

- COOL

- BRUTE

- **SHORT U**

u

PUT

PULL

oo

COOK

LOOK

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- Short U
- Watch the following video:
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eJ7dM_LU9t4
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **PRONOUNCE** THESE WORDS:

- PUT

- BOOK

- FOOT

- LOOK

- COULD

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- **QUIZ** Are these vowel sounds SHORT or LONG?

SOON

MOON

WHO

BOOK

PUT

GOOD

TOOK

RUDE

• THE SCHWA

untressed syllables

e

THE

BOTTLE

-ar

POPULAR

-er

BROTHER

-or

DOCTOR

a-

AGAIN

to-

TODAY

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

/ə/

about

photography

submit

tiger

- Schwa Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wg0P0oYkniE>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

Sounds of English: vowels (1)

- PRONOUNCE THESE WORDS:

- THE

- MOTHER

- AGAIN

- TODAY

- BANANA

- TOMORROW

- Schwa sound explained
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Yj-uAltQJk>
- Source: PodcastsinSounds Youtube

- QUIZ - WHERE ARE THE SCHWA SOUNDS?
- Father
- Enjoy
- Control
- Arrrive
- tiger
- again
- Cup of tea

• **THE SCHWA IN UNSTRESSED WORDS**

UNSTRESSED WORDS

**ARTICLES
PREPOSITIONS
PRONOUNS
AUXILIARIES**

the, a, an ...

Ex.: *the man, an apple*

of, for ...

Ex.: *from Spain, of England*

them, her ...

Ex.: *tell her, tell them*

can ...

Ex.: *I can dance*

- **Pronounce** the following sentences:
- THE CLASS IS GOOD
- TELL HER TO COME
- I CAN READ ENGLISH

PRONOUNCE

THE WORD

ELEVEN

eleven

/ɪˈlevən/

- Some humour:
- Eleven with Scottis Accent
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HbDnxzrbxn4>
- Source: The Scottish Comedy Channel (Youtube)

VOWEL SOUNDS

REVIEW

Sounds of English: vowels (2)

- **Match** words with same vowel sound

A collection of 25 blue rounded rectangular buttons, each containing a word. The words are: HALF, BUS, NOT, YOU, BIRD, CUT, TEN, HORSE, RAT, TWO, A, FLOOR, SHEEP, TWO, LIP, LEARN, FLOOR, THE, DOG, HAT, PUT, SIT, SEAT, LOOK, MEN.

- **PRONOUNCE** THE FOLLOWING WORDS – MINIMAL PAIRS – LONG AND SHORT
- HAT / HEART / HUT
- BED / BIRD
- SIT / SEAT
- POT / PORT
- LOOK / LUKE

**DIPHTHONGS
SHOULD BE PRONOUNCED AS
ONE SYLLABLE
TWO VOWEL SOUNDS
TOGETHER**

- **Pronounce** the following words:

- NEW
- BIER
- BEAR
- TOUR
- COW
- SNOW

The diphthongs in English

- | DIPHTHONGS | |
|------------|--------------|
| /eɪ/ | as in 'take' |
| /aɪ/ | as in 'buy' |
| /ɔɪ/ | as in 'boy' |
| /ɪə/ | as in 'fear' |
| /eə/ | as in 'care' |
| /əʊ/ | as in 'go' |
| /ʊə/ | as in 'poor' |
| /aʊ/ | as in 'cow' |

- VIDEO
- AU sound

- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9WDnVMQIaTs>

- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:
- Now
- Cow
- Round
- House
- About

- The ODD one
- Which of the following words is pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

DOUBT, ABOUT, LOUD, BOAT, NOW, COW

/aɪ/

-I- *I, find, child, hi, kind ...*

-Y *by, my, cry, why, shy ...*

-IGH- *right, night, bright, light ...*

-IE / -YE *die, lie, tie, pie / bye, dye ...*

-I-E *time, bite, quite*

-UY *buy, guy, eye....*

- AI sound
- Watch the following video
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hb8COxAtI14>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Youtube) (Youtube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:
- BYE
- BUY
- NIGHT
- TIME
- QUITE
- DIE
- DYE
- LIGHT
- RIGHT

- EI Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5FMPlqIFt9g>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:

- EIGHT
- TRAIN
- DATE
- WAIT
- MAY
- TODAY
- OKAY

- The ODD one!
- Which two words are pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

**angel, paper, pay, bright, snail, day,
rain, May, great, say, beer**

/ɔɪ/

 -OI: *noise, coin, toilet, point, voice ...*

 -OY *boy, toy, join, destroy, employ ...*

- OI Sound
- Watch the following video
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IFRrEI85IcM>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Youtube) (Youtube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:

- BOY
- OIL
- COIN
- CHOICE
- TOILET
- OYSTER

- The ODD one!
- Which word is pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

oil, toy, boy, coin, air, destroy, joy,

- Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0J7-5maJJlk>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Youtube) (Youtube)

- **Pronounce** the following sentence.

WHERE are MARY's PARENTS?

They are over THERE

- The ODD one
- Which two words are pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

**THERE, BEAR, HAIR, BEER, HARE,
NEAR, CARE, AIR, PAIR, WEAR**

- Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vC0h4S0YPJc>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Youtube) (Youtube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:
- HERE
- EAR
- DEAR
- NEAR
- BEER
- BEARD

- The ODD one
- Which TWO words are pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

**BEER, SINCERE, DEAR, BEAR, NEAR,
CARE, CLEAR, EAR, FEAR**

- Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r1BRCG0P9C8>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:

- GO
- NO
- SO
- LOW
- DON'T
- HELLO
- HOPE

- **The ODD one**

- Which TWO words are pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

**GO, NO, DO, SNOW, BLOW, BOAT,
HOPE, GOAT, LOUD, SMOKE**

- Sound
- Watch the following video:
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nHSqLuHrD-U>
- Source: BBC Learning English (Yotube)

- **Pronounce** the following words:

- TOURIST

- SURE

- ENSURE

- PURE

- The ODD one
- Which TWO words are pronounced with a different two-vowel sound:

SURE, PURE, CULTURE, TOUR, MANURE, CURE, PICTURE

• Match words with similar diphthong

THERE

NOW

PARENT

NOISE

HERE

BEER

HOUSE

HAIR

NO

BOY

BEAR

TOUR

ROAD

AIR

HARE

SURE

TRIPHTHONGS

aɪə (fire, tired, flyer)

aʊə (hour/our, power, tower)

eɪə (player, mayor)

əʊə (lower, widower)

ɔɪə (loyal, royal)

- **Pronounce** the following words:
- FIRE
- HIGHER
- FLOWER
- TOWER
- OUR
- LAWYER
- LOWER

Consonants in English

p PI <u>G</u>	b BE <u>D</u>	t TI <u>M</u> E	d DO <u></u>	tʃ CH <u>U</u> R <u>CH</u>	dʒ JU <u>D</u> GE	k KI <u>L</u> O	g GO <u></u>
f FI <u>V</u> E	v VE <u>R</u> Y	θ TH <u>I</u> NK	ð TH <u>E</u>	s SI <u>X</u>	z ZO <u>O</u>	ʃ SH <u>O</u> R <u>T</u>	ʒ CAS <u>U</u> AL
m MI <u>L</u> K	n NO <u></u>	ŋ SI <u>N</u> G	h HE <u>L</u> LO	l LI <u>V</u> E	r RE <u>A</u> D	w WI <u>N</u> DOW	j YE <u>S</u>

WORD STRESS

problem ●●

mistake ●●

error ●●

- **Pronounce**

- **Cat, dog**

- **English, Hello**

- **Banana , University**

Stress-
timed
rhythm

English

German

Dutch

Syllable-
timed
rhythm

Spanish

Italian

French

• John, remember the milk

• Juan, tomate la leche

- Watch the following video (Stress-timed)
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SR79TZbKRUU&t=22s>
- Source: British Council (Youtube)

DROPPED SYLLABLES

FAMILY /FAM-LY/

ASPIRIN /AS-PRIN/

SEPARATE /SEP-RET/

INTERESTING /IN-TRES-TING/

LABORATORY /LAB-RA-TO-RY/

PRONOUNCE AS 2 SYLLABLES

Word	Pronunciation
aspirin	AS prin
business	BUS ness
camera	CAM ra
Catholic	CATH lic
chocolate	CHOC lit
conference	CON frens
corporate	CORP rit
diamond	DI mond
diaper	DI per
different	DIFF rent
evening	EVE ning
family	FAM ly
favorite	FAV rit
general	GEN ral
interest	iN trest
separate	SEP rit
several	SEV ral
Wednesday	WENZ day

PRONOUNCE AS 3 SYLLABLES

comfortable	COMF ter ble
interesting	IN tres ting
temperature	TEM pa ture

PRONOUNCE AS 4 SYLLABLES

laboratory	LAB ra tor y
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- **Pronounce** clapping your hands
- SPAIN, STUDENT, SPEAK **(1 SYLLABLE)**
- EVERY, DIFFERENT, SEVERAL, CHOCOLATE, RESTAURANT **(2 SYLLABLES)**
- INTERESTING, COMFORTABLE, TEMPERATURE **(3 SYLLABLES)**

WORD STRESS

1. Depending on **MORPHOLOGY**
2. Depending on **grammatical CATEGORY**
3. Depending on English **VARIETY** (accent)

operate ● ● ●
apologise ● ● ● ● ●
ous ●
ary ● ●

Word stress

1. Word stress: morphology

- **COMPOUNDS**: always stress on **FIRST** syllable

- Pronounce:

- BLACKBOARD

- LAPTOP

- BEDROOM

- HOTDOG

- RAINBOW

- FIREMAN

- BASKETBALL

Prefixes

- **PREFIXES:** stress falls **AFTER** prefix

Prefix	Meaning	Examples
re-	again	rewrite
un-	not	unkind
pre-	before	premade
dis-	not, opposite of	dishonest
im-	not, opposite of	impolite

- **Pronounce:**

- FORGET
- FORGIVE
- UNDERSTAND
- RETURN

- DISHONEST

- PROPOSE
- TRANSFORM

suffixes

- With these **ENDINGS** the stress falls on **LAST syllable**

-EER

volunt**EER**

engin**EER**

-QUE

u**NIQUE**

an**TiQUE**

-OON

after**NOON**

typh**OON**

-AIRE

questionn**AIRE**

million**AIRE**

-EE

refer**EE**

refug**EE**

suffixes

- With these **ENDINGS** the stress falls on **syllable BEFORE** de suffix

-tion /
-sion

-ity /
-ety

-ic /
-ics /
-ical

-ian /
-ient

-ible /
-ial

tele**V**ision

au**T**HO**R**ity

e**L**AS**T**ic

poli**T**ician

im**P**OS**S**ible

ani**M**A**T**ion

va**R**ie**T**y

bio**L**O**G**ical

ma**G**ician

se**Q**U**E**N**T**ial

- **QUIZ**, WHERE DOES THE STRESS FALL, ON THE FIRST OR LAST SYLLABLE?

AFTERNOON

TELEVISION

MILLIONAIRE

COMMUNICATION

POLITICIAN

ACTION

POSSIBLE

ENGINEER

MAGICAL

REFUGEE

- Pronounce:

- *Good afternoon! You are watching BBC news*

- *The police detained the criminal yesterday afternoon in London. In a communication, the police informed that the criminal had killed the famous millionaire the week before.*

2. Words CHANGE THE stress DEPENDING ON grammar

- Some words are stressed differently **depending on the grammatical category:**

Nouns	Verbs
PR oject	pro J ECT
OB ject	ob J ECT
CON vict	con V ICT
PRE sent	pre S ENT
SUS pect	sus P ECT
RE cord	re C ORD
CON trast	con T RAST
IN sult	in S ULT
CON flict	con F LICT

- **Pronounce:**

- I liked your PREsent // I will preSENT my family to you

- There is a new World REcord // Please, reCORD your voices!

- That was a big INsult // Please, don't inSULT me!

STRONG AND WEAK FORMS

Content words

NOUNS

VERBS

ADJECTIVES

PRONOUNS

Function words

ARTICLES

PREPOSITIONS

ADVERBS

AUXILIARIES

modal verbs

weak form

strong form

can

kən

kæn

will

wɪl

wɪl

would

wəd

wʊd

shall

ʃəl

ʃæl

must

mʌst

mʌst

- **PRONOUNCE:**

- FISH AND CHIPS

- APPLES AND ORANGES

- BLUE AND YELLOW

-
- **Pronounce:**
 - Do you speak English?
 - Do you like bananas?
 - Can I go to the bathroom?
 - Can you tell me the time?

- Pronounce:

- HELLO

- GOOD MORNING

- GOOD AFTERNOON

- GOOD EVENING

- GOOD BYE

INTONATION

What is Intonation in English

Rhythm has a correlation
with ***Stress***.

Intonation has a correlation
with ***Pitch***.

How long have you been waiting for me?

How **long** have you been **wait**ing for me?

Rhythm is about timing.

Here's another way to picture rhythm.

Intonation is melody, or patterns of changes in pitch.

Here's another way to picture intonation.

English pronunciation

It's a beautiful day today

- Watch the following video and pay attention to the intonation:
-
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MIDwE3rYuiE>
- Source: Big Ban Theory (Yotube) – ‘I’m sorry’ intonation

• **LANGUAGES CAN BE:**

• **STRESS-TIMED**

ENGLISH

• **SYLLABLE-TIMED**

SPANISH

Class starts today.

Classes are starting tomorrow.

The classes should be starting this Monday.

Circle the STRESSED words in each sentence:

- Good afternoon, how are you?
- Can you help me, please?
- I like running and swimming every week
- If you learn this lesson, you will speak good English.

Pronounce:

- Good afternoon, how are you?
- Can you help me, please?
- I like running and swimming every week
- If you learn this lesson, you will speak good English.

STRONG

&

WEAK

FORMS

English pronunciation

- Draw a slash or dash to indicate the place of the pause:

The CLASS has been CANcelled

I can SPEAK ENglish and SPAnish

I CAN'T speak GERman

Can I GO to the BATHroom, please?

Do you KNOW the Tittle of this MOvie?

- Draw a slash or dash to indicate the place of the pause:

The CLASS has been CANcelled

I can SPEAK ENglish and SPANish

I CAN'T speak GERman

Can I GO to the BATHroom, please?

Do you KNOW the Title of this MOvie?

English pronunciation (BEATS)

1. The CLASS has been CANcelled

2. I can SPEAK ENglish and SPANish

* I CAN'T speak GERman

3. Can I GO to the BATHroom, please?

4. Do you KNOW the TITle of this MOvie?

INTONATION

- **CONTRASTIVE STRESS**
- **EMPHASIS**
- **SENSE (PRAGMATICS)**
- **INTERPRETING**

One Sentence, Different Meanings

- Are you going to eat **THAT**?

[Meaning: it's so big! / it's disgusting!]

- Are you going to **EAT** that?

[Meaning: I'm not sure that it's really 'food!']

- Are **YOU** going to eat that?

[Meaning: I thought you bought it for me!]

- **ARE** you going to eat that?

[Meaning: you are sitting here just looking ...]

-
- **Pronounce** the following sentence with some type of intonation (surprise, excitement, romantic, annoyed, etc). Your classmates will need to GUESS your intonation.
 - WHAT ARE YOU DOING?

- **Intonation:**

- **FOUR basic types:**

- **Falling Intonation** (↘)

- **Rising Intonation** (↗)

- **Rise-Fall Intonation** (↗↘)

- **Fall-Rise Intonation** (↘↗)

Falling Intonation (↘)

(The pitch of the voice **falls** at the end of the sentence.)

- **Statements:** The class starts at ↘ five
- **Commands:** Give me your ↘ paper
- **Wh-questions:** What country do you come ↘ from?
- **Exclamations:** That's a good ↘ point!

- **PRONOUNCE** WITH FALLING INTONATION

- I like this class
- Call me later.
- That's very interesting!
- Where are you from?
- What's your name?

Rising Intonation (↗)

(The pitch of the voice **rises** at the end of a sentence.)

- **Yes/No questions:** Have you finished ↗ already?
- **Questions tags that show uncertainty:** You're a new student, ↗ aren't you?

- **PRONOUNCE** (RISING WITH RISING INTONATION)

- ARE YOU HUNGRY?
- IS HE THE TEACHER?
- YOU ARE SPANISH, AREN'T YOU?
- YOU SPEAK ENGLISH, DON'T YOU?

• Rise-Fall Intonation (↗↘)

• (The intonation **rises** and then **falls**.)

• **Choices:** Do you speak ↗ French or ↘ English?

• **Lists:** I like ↗ football, tennis, basketball and ↘ volleyball

• **Conditional sentences:** If you have any ↗ problem, just ↘ contact me

- **PRONOUNCE (WITH RISE-FALL INTONATION)**

- I like apples, oranges and bananas
- Do you want to go to the theater or cinema?
- If it rains a lot, I'll stay home

- **Fall-Rise Intonation** (↘↗)

- (The voice **falls** and **rises** *usually within one word.*)

- **Hesitation/reluctance:** Did you give him your number? I don't quite ↘re↗member

- **Uncertainty/Doubt:** Should we ↘cop↗y the list?

- **PRONOUNCE** (RISING WITH RISING INTONATION)

- Should we do this activity?
- Would you like another coffee?

Stress by context

*I was so **angry** at my friend.*

*He **forgot** to call me on my **birthday**.*

*He said he **had** remembered, but that
it was **too** late to call.*

• PRONOUNCE:

- *I was so **angry** at my friend.*
- *He forgot to call me on my **birthday**.*
- *He said he **had** remembered, but that it was **too** late to call*

- **QUIZ:** Are the following *rise / fall / rise-fall / fall-rise*?
- Do we have class tomorrow?
- Why do you call me so early? It's Sunday –
- I've been studying English for 5 years-
- I like chocolate, coffee and cream –
- If you don't call me, I'll be mad at you –
- You can speak English, can't you? –
- Have you closed the door? –
- Don't say that again! -

- **QUIZ:** Are the following *rise / fall / rise-fall / fall-rise*?
- Do we have class tomorrow? Rise
- Why do you call me so early? It's Sunday – fall
- I've been studying English for 5 years- fall
- I like chocolate, coffee and cream – rise-fall
- If you don't call me, I'll be mad at you – rise-fall
- You can speak English, can't you? – rise
- Have you closed the door? – rise
- Don't say that again! - fall

- Watch the following video (Hamlet – different intonations)
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34ykFlfn1X4>
- Source: The Thespian Acting Engineer (Youtube)

CONNECTED SPEECH

Pronounce

- NICE TO MEET **T YOU**

- YOU SPEAK ENGLISH, DON'T **T YOU?**

- What is connected speech?

Sequence of sounds in Spoken English

Fluent speech flows with a rhythm

Words bump into each other

I've got to go =

What's up? =

wassup

- Pronounce

- Tell **them** to call me soon
- Give **her** my number
- Watch **him** while he plays outside
- Tell **her** to stop it

1. ASSIMILATION

2.LINKING R

3.ELISION & CATENATION

4.COLLOQUIAL FORMS (SLANG)

English pronunciation

1

ASSIMILATION

What did you do last night?

/d/ + /j/ = /dʒ/

/t/ + /j/ = /tʃ/

did + you = /di dʒu: /

English pronunciation

NICE TO MEET **YOU**

I MISS **YOU**

COULD **YOU** OPEN THE WINDOW, PLEASE?

WHAT **YOU** NEED IS A GOOD JOB

YOU SPEAK ENGLISH, DON'T **YOU**?

Pronounce

- NICE TO MEET **YOU**
- **COULD YOU** OPEN THE WINDOW, PLEASE?
- **WHAT YOU** NEED IS A GOOD JOB
- **YOU SPEAK ENGLISH, DON'T YOU?**

2

LINKING R

Non-rhotic

[fɑ:]
[pɔ:t]
[stɜ:]
[stɜ:rɪŋ]
[raɪt]

Rhotic

[fɑ:r]
[pɔ:rt]
[stɜ:r]
[stɜ:rɪŋ]
[raɪt]

far
port
stir
stirring
right

Far away

fɑ: əweɪ > fɑ:r əweɪ

More ice

mɔ: raɪs > mɔ:r aɪs

later

later on

/'leɪ.tə/

/'leɪ.tər ɒn/

- **Pronounce** (Linking R):

- The tower of London is very famous
- There are four eagles in the mountain
- My mother-in-law is here in my room

3

ELISION

Should you say:

lovely

3 syllables

or

lovely

2 syllables

English pronunciation

3

ELISION

friends	/ <u>frɛndz</u> /	['frɛns]
Christmas	/ 'krɪstməs /	['krɪsməs]
sandwich	/ 'sændwɪtʃ /	['sænwɪtʃ]
grandmother	/ 'grændmʌðər /	['grænmʌðər]
grandpa	/ 'grændpɑː /	['grænpɑː]
grandma	/ 'grændmɑː /	['grænmɑː]
grandson	/ 'grændsʌn /	['grænsʌn]
grandparent	/ 'grændpeərənt /	['grænpɛərənt]
mustn't	/ 'mʌstnt /	['mʌsnt]
handsome	/ 'hændsəm /	['hænsəm]

CATENATION

C + V

get up -getup

an apple -- napple

salt and pepper -sal tanpepper

fish and chips - fish nchips

- **Pronounce** (elision & catenation)

- Ev(e)ry ev(e)ning is diff(e)rent

- Salt and pepper

- I like fish and chips

COLLOQUIAL FORMS (SLANG) - contractions

gonna

wanna

gotta

ain't

lemme

wannabe

gimme

doncha

• Match

GONNA

Don't know

HAFTA

WANNA

GIMME

Kind of

Want to

Have got to

GOTTA

DUNNO

Going to

Have to

What's up?

Give me

KINDA

WASSAP

English pronunciation

- What are you going to do? →
 - Whatcha going to do? →
 - **Whatcha gonna do?**
-
 - Do you want a beer?
 - Do you wanna beer?
 - D'you wanna beer?
 - D'ya wanna beer?
 - Ya wanna beer?
 - **Wanna beer?**

Wanna – I want to

I wanna talk to him

I wanna kiss you

I wanna go to the cinema

- **Pronounce:**

- I just wanna be alone
- We wanna live in London
- You wanna go to the cinema tonight?
- I wanna be with you the rest of my life

Gonna – I want to

I'm gonna talk to him

I'm gonna miss you

I'm gonna eat now

-
- Pronounce:
 - I'm gonna order some food
 - We're gonna take a walk after class
 - She's gonna travel to London next week

Gotta – I want to

I gotta go

I gotta finish this soon

I gotta tell you the truth

- **Pronounce**

- You gotta go now
- Sorry, I gotta go to the bathroom
- I've gotta catch the bus or I'll be late

Dunno – I don't know

Do you know if we have have class
next week?

I dunnot

• Pronounce

- I dunno if I'll pass my exam
- I dunno who she is
- I dunno the name of the movie
- I dunno what the teacher said

wudja– Would you

Wudja like to come to my party?

Wudja like to visit us next week?

- **Pronounce:**

- Wudja call me later?
- Wudja tell him you don't love him?
- Wudja like to go to the concert?

Kinda – kind of

He's kinda stupid

This kinda reminds me my trip to
Spain

•Pronounce

- I think you kinda like this class
- It gets kinda crazy during the festival
- I'm kinda tired to wait for her

Hafta – have to

I hafta to leave

You're gonna hafta tell her the
truth

- **Pronounce:**

- I hafta go shopping

- I hafta clean my house

- I hafta to leave soon or I'll miss the bus

Musta – must to

I musta go there

You musta be tired

Musta been great

- **Pronounce**

- He musta been surprised when you called him
- You musta been shocked
- Musta been terrible for you

• Pronounce

- I'm **gonna** call (h)im now and tell (h)im the truth
- I **gotta** go, I **hafta** buy something
- You **wanna** go to the cinema tonight? // I **dunno** // ok, **gimme** a call